

AGREEMENT ON PARTICIPATING IN CRAFTH CIRCULAR SPRINT 2021

By and between:

Aalto University Foundation sr represented by ...

ADDRESS

VAT no:

Contact person: *name*, [email](#)

(hereinafter "Aalto")

A foundation incorporated and existing under the laws of Finland

AND

COMPANY

ADDRESS

VAT

Contact person:

(hereinafter "Company")

Company and AALTO will be hereinafter referred to jointly as "Parties".

1. Scope of the Agreement

1.1 Aalto is partner in the EIT RawMaterials funded project CRAFTH: CiRcular design & manuFacTuring Hackathon between 1.1.-31.12.2021(hereinafter "**Project**"). As part of the Project, Aalto will arrange a local iteration of the Circular Sprint event from 7 to 17 September 2021 (hereinafter "**Design Sprint**"). The term "Design Sprint" refers to an event where participants solve challenges set by the Organizers and their partners over a fixed period of time. Thematically the Circular Sprint event concentrates on circular economy and additive manufacturing, also known as 3D printing.

Companies participating to the Design Sprint (hereinafter "**Companies**") will provide challenges or problem (hereinafter "**Challenges**") to the Design Sprint for the participants of the event (hereinafter "**Participants**") to solve. Participants are individual doctoral students, master's students, or industry professionals who have applied to the event via the event website. By applying to the event, participants have agreed to the terms of conditions: <https://www.crafth.eu/terms-and-conditions>.

1.2 Company will be participating to the Design Sprint by providing its own Challenge and involvement in the Circular Sprint event as defined in this Agreement.

1.3 For the clarity it is mentioned that this Agreement will not bind the Participants of the Design Sprint. If Company needs to protect its material as confidential or wishes to receive rights

to the results generated by the Participants, it needs to agree this separately directly with the individual Participants.

2. Obligations of the Parties

2.1 Aalto's obligations

Aalto is the Organizer of the Aalto edition Design Sprint. The intention is to have Design Sprint partially online and partially at the premises of Aalto. If the pandemic situation (Covid19) requires, Aalto might organize the Design Sprint only as an online event. Aalto is responsible for general planning, preparations, communication, and execution of the online and on-site activities together with the Project consortium and the Company. Aalto will be responsible for recruiting Participants to the event. The Parties acknowledge that Aalto is not able to guarantee a specific number of participants, nor Participants with a certain expertise profile.

2.2 Company's obligations:

Before the Event:

Company will provide a Challenges to the Design Sprint for the Participants to solve. The contents of the Challenges are agreed together with the Company and Aalto.

A Challenge, in the context of the Design Sprint, is preferred to involve the following elements:

- *Circular Economy:* The Challenge attempts to improve the global net sustainability of an existing Company product, process, or service according to the circular economy principles. Alternatively, a Challenge may be an exploration of new such applications.
- *3D printing:* At the time of Challenge proposal, a potential solution may clearly benefit from 3D printing (additive manufacturing) as a manufacturing method, process step, or service step to increase product circularity
- *Tangibility:* The event Participants will be able to prototype their proposed solution or a service with a physical prototype
- *Business:* The proposed challenge should be economically feasible now or in the near future
- *Sprint Feasibility:* The amount of provided background material and focus of the Challenge is adjusted in a way that a Participant team may provide meaningful solutions during the event with a limited time

Company defines and summarizes the Challenges in written form (3-5 sentences) and provides Aalto with supplementary graphical content to advertise the event.

During the event:

The Company must support the event and the Participant team who attempt to solve the Company Challenge with a dedicated person(s) and with Company material necessary to work with the proposed Challenge. Such material may contain but is not limited to product documents, 3D models, service descriptions, material data, or information about logistics. The Company decides what material it wishes to provide the Participants.

The dedicated person is required to:

- Introduce the Company Challenge with a maximum 30-minute graphical presentation during an online meeting for the Design Sprint Participants and Organizers.
- Be available for an interview with the Participant team (maximum 60 minutes) to discuss about the Challenge
- Attend two feedback sessions (maximum 60 minutes each) with the Participant team to discuss their Challenge process and prototypes
- Attend the final day presentations 17.9. (2-3 hours) and provide feedback for the Participant team on their proposed solution

The schedule of the obligations during the event will be communicated and agreed verbally before the event.

2.3 Company provides Aalto a non-exclusive, limited right to use content and material, which the Company has provided to be used in the Design Sprint. Aalto's right to use the logo or any other Company's trademarks, trade names or any such other intellectual property rights is limited only to the purpose of Aalto to fulfil its obligations defined in this Agreement and will cease immediately with the termination hereof. The Company may not use the logo or any other Aalto's trademark without a separate written permission.

2.4 Company will grant Aalto non-exclusive, limited right to use its content, which has been provided for the Design Sprint, including but not limited to marketing material, Company information, and Challenge background information in the marketing of future events, articles, or scientific publications. Aalto is required to communicate and agree the formatting and further use of such content with the Company on a case-by-case basis.

3. Intellectual property rights

3.1 Intellectual Property Rights (hereinafter IPR) mean all forms of intellectual property protection, including patents, utility models, trademarks, copyrights, chip topography rights, design rights (including unregistered design rights), as well as know-how and applications for the same.

3.2 No existing IPR or other rights of the Parties shall be granted or transferred to the other Party, unless otherwise agreed in this Agreement.

3.3 All IPR produced at the event by the Participants is owned solely by the Participants.

4. Term of the agreement

4.1 This agreement will come in force from the later signature and will be in force until parties have executed their obligations, but no later than 31.12.2021.

4.2 All terms and conditions of this agreement, like IPRs and right to publish, which by their nature are meant to remain valid also after the termination of the agreement, shall remain valid independent of the termination of the agreement.

5. Confidentiality

5.1 All information received by a Party from another Party whether orally, in writing, or in electronic or any other form shall be deemed confidential provided, that such information is clearly marked as confidential. The Party disclosing oral information intended as confidential information shall, at the time of disclosure, state that the information is confidential and within fourteen (14) days provide confirmation in writing of its confidential nature (hereinafter 'Confidential Information'). The Parties shall not exchange or transfer to another Party any personal data as defined in the EU general data protection regulation (2016/679), unless otherwise agreed in writing by the Parties.

5.2 The Parties undertake to treat Confidential Information confidential, undertake not to disclose Confidential Information to third parties and undertake not to use Confidential Information for purposes other than the fulfilment of their rights and obligations under this Agreement. The Parties shall have a right to disclose Confidential Information to such experts and individual members of the steering group and to subcontractors, who are under a confidentiality obligation according to law or who have agreed in writing to comply with the confidentiality obligations of this Agreement, if such disclosure is required to fulfil their obligations under this Agreement.

5.3 The confidentiality obligation does not, however, apply to information that:

- (a) was in the public domain or generally available to the public at the time of disclosure,
- (b) has become part of the public domain or generally available to the public subsequent to disclosure of the Confidential Information through no fault of the receiving Party,
- (c) was known to the receiving Party before receiving the information from the disclosing Party,
- (d) was obtained from a third party without any confidentiality obligations,
- (e) has been developed independently or together with a third party without breach of the confidentiality obligations of this Consortium Agreement, or

(f) has to be disclosed or made public under law or other statute or order of a court of law or other authority.

5.4 The obligations of Section 5 shall remain in effect for a period of five (5) years from the disclosure of Confidential Information, however no more than three (3) years from the termination of this Agreement.

6. Limitation of liability

6.1 Notwithstanding the above, the Parties shall not be liable for indirect or consequential damages or losses caused in the execution of the Agreement towards the other Party, with the exception of damages arising from the breach of the confidentiality obligations of this Agreement. Indirect loss refers to damage caused by: the reduction or interruption in production or turnover; other loss arising because the results cannot be used as intended; loss of profit arising because a contract with a third party has been lost or breached; loss due to damage to property other than results, or other similar loss that is difficult to foresee. The aggregate liability of a Party under the Agreement shall be limited to ten thousand (10.000) euros. Limitation of liability shall not apply to damages caused willfully or due to gross negligence.

6.2 A Party is not liable for any delay or non-performance of its obligations due to force majeure. Any event, which prevents or renders the performance of the Agreement unreasonably difficult within the time specified, shall be considered force majeure. Such events include, but are not limited to, war, insurrection, epidemic, pandemic, natural disaster, interruption in the general energy supply, fire, strike, embargo, material restriction imposed by the government budget or by the government on the activities of a Party, the termination of employment, serious illness or accident of a person who is essential for the execution of the Agreement, or other equally significant and uncommon reason beyond a Party's control. A delay on the part of a subcontractor for the above reason shall also be deemed to constitute force majeure.

6.3 A Party is entitled to postpone its performance or terminate the Agreement, if an event of force majeure results in delay. The Agreement may be terminated only if the delay is essential.

7. Dispute resolution and applicable law

7.1 All disputes relating to this Agreement (including disputes relating specifically to this clause) shall be governed by and construed in accordance with Finnish legislation without any regard to its principles and rules on conflict of laws. Both Parties have an obligation to try and reach an agreement before initiating any legal procedures. Should an agreement not be reached, the disagreement shall be settled in the District Court of Helsinki, Finland.

8. Entire agreement

8.1 This Agreement constitutes the entire agreement between the Parties with respect to the subject matter hereof and supersedes all prior agreements, proposals, undertakings, and other representations and communications between the Parties.

9. Miscellaneous

9.1 Aalto is not liable for any actions taken by the Participants. If, for example, the Company wishes to commit a/the Participant(s) to confidentiality or to other obligations and/or wants for the Participant to transfer rights to the Company, the Company must make an agreement with the Participant(s).

9.2 The Agreement may only be amended in writing by signatures of the duly authorized representatives of the parties.

9.3 No Party shall, without the prior written consent of the other Party, assign or transfer the Agreement in whole or in part to a third party.

9.4 If one or more of the provisions of this Agreement are found to be invalid, the validity and enforceability of the remaining provisions of this Agreement shall not in any way be affected or impaired. The Parties shall replace the invalid provision by a new provision that meets the intention of the Parties when signing this Agreement.

Signatures

Parties have duly executed this Agreement by the signatures of their authorized representatives. This Agreement may be transmitted by electronic means as a pdf copy, in which case each electronic copy will be effective as if an original.

SIGNATURES

_____.____.2021
Espoo, Finland

_____.____.2021
Espoo, Finland
